

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Evaluating the Impact of Formulation Parameters on Permeation of Clotrimazole from Topical Creams

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 19 Jan 2026

Keywords:

Clotrimazole, Cremophor RH40, Tween40, emulsifying agent and permeation enhancer.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.18298169

ABSTRACT

Objective: The objective of the current study is to examine the effects of emulsifying agents (Cremophore RH40, Tween 40) and permeation enhancers (l-Menthol) on cream formulations. The goal is to develop a formulation that is both safe and capable of delivering the drug locally at an effective concentration to achieve its intended therapeutic effect. **Methodology:** In the present work was applied to study the effect of varying concentration of Cremophore RH40, Tween 40 and permeation enhancers (l-Menthol). All of the prepared cream formulations were evaluated for its physicochemical parameters like pH, spreadability, viscosity, drug content and in vitro diffusion studies. Further, the optimized formulation was evaluated for in vitro anti-fungal activity and stability studies. **Results:** Different formulations of the cream were prepared using different concentration emulsifying agent and all the findings obtained were within the prescribed limit with less diffusion of drug. Out of nine different formulations, F9 was chosen as the optimized formula was included with menthol as penetration enhancer. The concentration of permeation enhancer significantly affects the critical parameters of cream formulation like cumulative amount released at 12 hours. In vitro permeation study showed that menthol enhanced the transdermal absorption of drug from cream formulation. The topical cream formulation developed in this study showed good anti-fungal activity and stable for 3 months. **Conclusion:** The development of topical cream to have localized effects appears to be very advisable and beneficial over conventional routes of provides the drug administration for the effective treatment of Skin infections

INTRODUCTION

Topical/transdermal drug delivery refers to delivery of drugs via skin and is an attractive alternative to conventional methods such as oral

and parenteral routes. Advantages associated with topical/transdermal delivery include non-invasive delivery, by pass of first pass metabolism, prolonged duration of action, reduced dosing

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

frequency, constant levels of drug in the plasma, reduced drug toxicity/ adverse events, improved patient compliance, and others. However, skin acts as a major barrier for entry of drugs and foreign compounds due to presence of stratum corneum, a thin keratin rich layer (15µm) of dead cells embedded in an intricate lipid environment made of cholesterol, ceramides, and free fatty acids. In addition, several other factors such as physicochemical properties of the drug (lipophilicity, solubility, molecular weight or size and hydrogen bonding) and characteristics of a formulation/vehicle or a drug delivery system influence the permeation.¹

The site of clotrimazole action is the stratum corneum where the pathogens reside. However, the specialized nature of the stratum corneum makes it an efficient barrier to drug molecules. Therefore, stratum corneum penetration is the rate limiting step in percutaneous drug absorption. Clotrimazole is usually formulated as a 1% cream, lotion, spray or solution for treatment of skin fungal infections. However, the commercially available topical products of clotrimazole have the limitations of low skin retention and deposition. Since clotrimazole is poorly water-soluble, it requires a proper vehicle to improve its topical absorption. Colloidal drug carriers such as microemulsions, vesicular carriers including liposomes, ectosomes and noisome as well as both lipidic and polymeric particulate carrier systems were developed for topical delivery of clotrimazole.²

Creams are widely used in the cosmetic and pharmaceutical fields for the topical administration of hydrophilic and lipophilic active ingredients. There exists different type of emulsions e.g. water-in-oil., oil-in-water, water-in-oil-in-water, oil-in-water-in- oil. Furthermore, emulsions are thermodynamically unstable and

necessitate an emulsifier for the formation and stabilization.

The effect of the vehicle on dermal and transdermal delivery:

It has been recognized that the vehicle in which the permeant is applied to the skin has a distinctive effect on the dermal and transdermal delivery of active ingredients. Despite the fact that studies have been performed to investigate the vehicle effect on skin penetration, it is still not fully understood, especially for more complex formulations such as emulsions. In addition, the task of formulating a topical formulation not only includes the optimization for delivery of the active ingredient but also the fulfillment of the requirements for chemical and physical stability, non-toxicity and aesthetic acceptability.³

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

Clotrimazole was procured from Yarrow Chem Products, Mumbai, India. Carbopol-940, Cremophor RH-40, Tween-40, isopropyl myristate, cetyl alcohol, benzyl alcohol, and triethanolamine were obtained from S.D. Fine-Chem Limited, India. All the materials and excipients used in the study were of analytical grade and were used as received without further purification.

Methods:

Pre formulation study:

Pre formulation study is the process of optimizing the delivery of drug through determination of physicochemical properties of the new compound that could affect drug performance and development of an efficacious, stable and safe dosage form. Pre formulation study is the first step in formulation of any dosage form. Prior to the development of the dosage forms the pre

formulation study was carried out. It gives the information needed to define the nature of the drug substance and provide a framework for the drug combination with pharmaceutical excipients in the dosage form. Hence, pre formulation studies were performed for the obtained sample of drug for identification and compatibility studies.⁴

Determination of melting point:

Melting point of drug was determined by taking a small quantity of drug in capillary tube sealed at one end and placed in digital melting point apparatus and the temperature was slowly increased with simultaneous observation of the sample. The temperature at which drug starts melting point was recorded as melting point. This process was repeated two more times. The mean of three reading was recorded.⁵

DRUG-EXCIPIENT COMPATIBILITY STUDIES FT-IR studies

FTIR spectroscopy helps to determine any chemical interaction between drug and excipients used in formulation. FT-IR spectroscopy was conducted using a Shimadzu FTIR spectrophotometer and spectrum was recorded in the wavelength region of 4000 400cm⁻¹. The procedure consisted of dispersing a sample i.e. 2mg (drug alone, polymer alone, and mixture of drug, polymer and non-volatile solvent) in 100 mg KBr and compressing into disc's by applying a pressure of 5 tones for 5 min into hydraulic press. The pellet was placed in the light path and the spectrum was recorded. All spectra were collected as an average of 3 scans at a resolution of 2cm⁻¹.⁶

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) Analysis 7-8:

DSC (Perkin-Elmer thermal analysis) studies were carried out in order to characterize the physical state of drugs. Sample of pure drug and physical mixture were placed in the aluminum pans and thematically sealed. The heating rate was 10°C per misusing nitrogen as pure gas. The DSC instrument was calibrated for temperature using indium. In addition, the enthalpy calibration indium was sealed in aluminum pan with sealed empty pans as reference.

Analytical Method: -

Preparation of reagents:

Potassium dihydrogen phosphate 0.2M:

27.218 grams of potassium dihydrogen phosphate was dissolved in little quantity of distilled water and volume adjusted to produce 1000 ml.

Sodium hydroxide 0.2 M:

8 grams of NaOH was dissolved in distilled water and volume adjusted to produce 1000 ml.

Preparation of phosphate buffer pH 7.4 solution:

Place 50 ml of 0.2M KH₂PO₄ in a 200 ml volumetric flask, add 39.1 ml of 0.2 M NaOH and volume adjusted to produce 1000 ml.

Preparation of standard stock solution of (1000µg/ml) clotrimazole:

Standard stock solution of clotrimazole was prepared by dissolving accurately weighed 100 mg of clotrimazole using pH 7.4 buffers in 100 ml volumetric flask. The volume was then made up to 100 ml by using phosphate buffer pH 7.4 to obtain the solution 1000 µg/ml.

Determination of analytical wavelength of clotrimazole:

10ml above stock solution was pipetted out and transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask. The volume was then made up to 100 ml with phosphate buffer pH 7.4. The resulting solution containing 100µg/ml was scanned between 200-400 nm. The wavelength of drug as λ_{max} was selected.

From the standard stock solution, a series of dilutions were prepared using phosphate buffer pH 7.4 to get concentration of 10-50 µg/ml. The absorbance of these solutions was measured using UV-spectrophotometer. Standard curve was obtained by plotting absorbance vs. drug concentration.

Calibration curve of clotrimazole in phosphate buffer pH 7.4:

Table No.1: Formulation Ingredients and their required quantities

INGREDIENTS (%)	Formulations									
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
Clotrimazole	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Carbopol-940	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Cremophor RH -40	2.5	2.5	2.5	5	5	5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5
Tween 40	1	2.5	5	1	2.5	5	1	2.5	5	5
Iso propyl myosterate	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Cetyl alcohol	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Benzyl alcohol	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Distilled water	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Triethanolamine	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s

Evaluation Parameters 9-15:

Physical appearance and pH:

Prepared creams were checked for their clarity and the pH was measured using a calibrated digital pH meter at 37°C. All measurements were made in triplicate.

Percentage yield:

The obtained gels were weighted and %yield was determined by the following equation.

$$\text{percent yield} = \frac{\text{actual yield}}{\text{theoretical yield}} \times 100\%$$

Spreadability:

For the determination of spreadability, excess of sample was applied between the two glass slides

and was compressed to uniform thickness by placing 100g weight for 5 min. Weight (50 g) was added to the pan. The time required to separate the two slides,

i.e the time in which the upper glass slide moves over the lower plate was taken as measure of spreadability(S)⁷.

$$S = M \times L / T,$$

Where,

- M = weight tide to upper slide,
- L = length moved on the glass slide,
- T = time taken.

Viscosity measurement of prepared cream:

The viscosity of the all-prepared creams was determined by using Brookfield digital viscometer

(Model no LVDV 2P230) using 10g of cream. Measurements were performed using suitable spindle and the temperature was maintained at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The viscosity was read directly from the viscometer display. All measurements were made in triplicate.

Determination of drug content:

1gm of prepared cream was dissolved in 5ml of pH 7.4 buffer solution and volume was made up to 100ml phosphate buffer pH 7.4. After suitable dilution the absorbance was measured by UV spectrophotometer (Shimadzu) at 262 nm.

In-vitro drug release:

The dialysis technique using cellophane membrane was used to study *in-vitro* release. Prior to diffusion studies, the dialysis membrane was soaked overnight in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer solution. 1gm of cream was placed on dialysis membrane, which was sealed on one side and one side opened. The dialysis tube was placed in a glass beaker containing 50 ml of pH 7.4 phosphate buffer solution. The release studies were performed at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and stirred at 50 rpm using magnetic stirrer. The 5 ml of sample was withdrawn at different time interval and was replaced with same volume of pH 7.4 phosphate buffer to maintain the sink condition. The samples were filtered through Whatman filter paper (No.41) and solutions were analyzed using UV Spectrophotometer after suitable dilution. Cumulative percentage drug release was determined by using standard graph.

Stability Test:

The stability of optimized formulation was studied at different temperatures. Cream was stored in well tight closed container and maintained at oven temperature ($40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) and $75 \pm 5\%$ RH for 3 months as per ICH guidelines. Change in the appearance and drug content of the stored cream was investigated after storage. The data presented are the mean of three determinations

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation study:

Melting point:

The melting point of Clotrimazole was determined by capillary method using digital melting point apparatus (in triplicate) and melting point found to be $145-150^\circ\text{C}$. Thus obtained melting point is in agreement with literature melting point which confirms the purity of drug.

Compatibility study:

FT-IR studies:-

The preformulation study was carried out to study the compatibility of the pure Clotrimazole with the polymers Carbopol and Cetyl alcohol. The individual spectra of the pure drug and in combination with excipients are shown in figure no.1 and 2. In IR spectra of Clotrimazole major peaks of functional groups were found at various wavelengths. In the physical mixture, the principle peaks were approximately matched with the pure drug principle peaks. Hence, it can be concluded that there was no possible interactions between the drug and excipients.

Table No.2 : Major peaks of Clotrimazole and physical mixture of IR spectra

INGREDIENTS	C-H	C=N	C=C	C-N str	C-H bending
Clotrimazole	3058.67	1583.05	1435.97	1081.22	751.55
Physical mixtures of Clotrimazole + Carbopol	3056.89	1440.95	1440.95	1082.11	752.51

Figure No.1: FTIR Spectra of Pure Drug Clotrimazole

Figure No.2: FTIR spectra of Physical Mixture of Drug and polymers

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC):-

Any possible drug polymer interaction can be studied by thermal analysis. The DSC patterns of pure Clotrimazole and its physical mixture are shown in Fig. 3 and 4 Pure Clotrimazole showed a sharp endothermic peak at 159.14°C corresponding to its melting point. There was

negligible change in the melting endotherms of the physical mixture of drug with polymers (156.67°C) compared to pure drug. This observation further supports the IR spectroscopy results, which indicated the absence of any interactions between the drug and additives used in the preparation.

Figure No.3: DSC of Pure drug Clotrimazole:

Figure No.4: DSC of Physical Mixture of drug and polymers

Table No.3: Standard Calibration data of Clotrimazole:

Sr. No.	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance $AM \pm SD$
1.	0	0 ± 0.000
2.	2	0.129 ± 0.033
3.	4	0.255 ± 0.060
4.	6	0.372 ± 0.085
5.	8	0.491 ± 0.109
6.	10	0.623 ± 0.139

Figure No.5: Standard Calibration curve of Clotrimazole

Table No.4: Evaluation Parameters of Clotrimazole cream

Formulation code	Appearance	% yield	Surface pH	Viscosity (cps $\times 103$)	Spreadability (gm/sec)	Drug content (%)
F1	Non- Transparent	73.3	6.5	656.61	15.12	96.7 ± 0.745
F2	Non- Transparent	79.2	6.7	669.29	13.89	94.2 ± 0.681
F3	Non- Transparent	72.52	6.6	672.84	14.53	93.95 ± 0.874
F4	Non- Transparent	77.44	6.7	681.11	13.74	94.32 ± 2.410
F5	Non- Transparent	71.56	6.6	684.74	13.98	92.33 ± 0.850
F6	Non- Transparent	76.63	6.8	687.11	13.25	92.62 ± 20402
F7	Non- Transparent	74.77	6.9	682.80	12.98	92.5 ± 3.294
F8	Non- Transparent	78.02	7.0	685.17	12.51	96.7 ± 1.284
F9	Non- Transparent	80.12	6.8	697.39	13.47	95.95 ± 0.956
F10	Non- Transparent	89.25	6.8	693.76	14.41	97.82 ± 1.172

Diffusion Study:-

The cumulative amount of drug released from creams were determined and plotted in Figure 6. Each data point represents the mean of 6 determinations. The amount of drug was constant in all different cream formulation. Among all cream formulations, formulations containing lower concentration of Cremophore RH40 and showed the less release of drug in 12hr and formulations containing higher Cremophore RH40 and showed the more release of drug in 12 hr. and

that is not maximum, and by the inclusion of tween-40 and penetration enhancer maximum release we can observe .Hence, higher concentration formulation was Selected for preparing cream formulations to study the effect of menthol as penetration enhancer. A marked effect of surfactants, concentration of Cremophor RH40 and concentration of Tween 40 on drug permeation was observed when it was incorporated cream formulations. The cumulative amount permeated at 12 hours of drug was optimized from cream formulation.

Table No.5: In-vitro drug release profile of Clotrimazole cream from (F1-F5):

TIME	FORMULATION CODE (Cumulative release %)				
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
0	0.000±0.000	0.000±0.000	0.000±0.000	0.000±0.000	0.000±0.000
10	2.06±0.339	0.7±0.434	0.86±2.441	0.8±3.179	0.9±1.212
20	4.19±0.956	1.46±2.157	1.35±3.893	1.16±2.416	1.8±0.421
30	5.08±0.329	2.26±0.899	2.21±1.671	1.65±3.412	2.58±2.648
45	7.9±1.558	3.66±1.474	3.54±1.644	2.55±0.627	3.95±0.415
60	10.06±2.364	4.7±0.355	4.54±1.544	3.06±0.606	5.27±1.146
90	12.4±0.498	6.97±0.916	5.16±1.246	4.2±1.629	7.74±1.996
120	14.17±1.089	9.15±1.327	7.36±2.106	5.15±2.676	14.85±2.535
150	16.1±1.134	10.96±1.673	9.75±3.226	6.67±3.969	17.6±4.594
180	18.4±2.262	11.76±1.796	11.2±4.171	8.3±5.656	21.36±5.967
210	20±3.391	14.6±4.177	13.64±2.156	10±3.047	23.32±4.841
240	21.4±2.058	17.86±0.758	20.04±3.197	11.5±3.604	27.13±2.712
270	23.5±0.639	19.72±3.091	22.6±1.905	14.2±0.774	33±1.974
300	25.5±5.442	21.44±2.216	26.5±3.814	17.3±1.694	37.6±2.197
330	27.6±1.835	24.12±2.909	28.6±0.498	20.4±3.956	41.15±5.285
360	30.3±2.614	27.56±2.112	31.8±2.613	24.4±0.075	45.63±3.284
420	35.8±0.704	33.61±2.394	37.42±3.687	32.4±0.709	54.5±3.118
480	43±0.284	45.6±2.821	47.8±4.173	47.4±4.457	56±0.497
540	52.96±2.359	56.2±3.462	54.91±3.805	50±0.497	59.8±0.706
600	58.15±1.211	58±1.346	59.4±1.981	53±1.764	62.5±3.044
660	60.6±3.749	61.9±3.185	63.5±3.251	54±1.907	67.8±2.407
720	65.12±1.206	65±1.345	69.6±1.974	55.8±0.704	69.5±0.358

In-vitro drug release profile of Clotrimazole cream from (F6-F10):

TIME	FORMULATION CODE (Cumulative release %)				
	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
0	0±0.000	0±0.000	0±0.000	0±0.000	0±0.000
10	0.7±1.276	0.7±1.275	0.7±0.358	5±1.487	1.6±1.485
20	1.82±2.498	1.7±2.195	1.16±1.049	2.2±1.415	2.3±1.417
30	2.7±2.619	2.7±2.686	1.97±1.995	3±0.639	3±0.635
45	4.2±0.142	3.9±4.950	3.92±2.044	4.1±1.065	4.2±1.062
60	5.3±1.768	5.2±2.688	5.4±0.849	5.07±0.878	5.05±0.874

90	7.4±0.708	7.2±5.021	6.39±2.772	7.23±2.185	7.24±2.183
120	8.8±3.395	8.7±4.668	7.67±3.285	8.62±4.024	8.62±4.024
150	11.2±4.526	11.2±3.748	8.78±3.416	10.8±5.447	10.8±5.445
180	18.6±4.876	17.8±1.699	11.07±2.275	14.3±2.756	14.3±2.759
210	24.2±1.556	22.7±5.236	16.07±4.392	19.2±3.185	19.2±3.182
240	29.3±3.819	27.5±4.948	19.8±4.524	27.55±1.8454	27.54±1.843
270	34.4±3.746	33.2±3.746	28.5±2.614	30.3±4.877	30.3±4.876
300	38.4±0.072	37.6±2.261	40.6±3.465	42.32±1.404	42.32±1.406
330	43.5±3.890	42.7±1.768	48.2±3.536	49.8±4.665	49.6±4.665
360	48.5±2.970	47.4±1.205	57.80±1.422	59.5±3.819	59.8±3.814
420	50.2±3.607	53.5±2.334	63.37±2.065	65±2.758	65±2.756
480	52.7±2.898	64.5±2.334	70.4±2.829	68±2.547	70±2.546
540	55.7±2.334	68.1±2.758	72.7±3.887	74±7.285	76±7.282
600	57.6±5.446	70.3±3.26	74.7±2.618	75±4.872	82±4.877
660	60.5±3.253	72.4±2.756	75.4±2.263	76.6±5.52	93.4±5.516
720	62.3±1.483	74.2±1.768	75.6±0.423	77.9±0.354	97.3±0.354

Figure No.6: In-Vitro diffusion profile of Formulation F1 to F10

Drug Release Kinetics:

In order to investigate the drug release mechanism, the drug release data fitted to models representing zero order, first order, Higuchi square root of time and Peppas model. The linear regression analysis are summarized in table no.6. The examination of co-efficient of determination (r^2) values for different formulation indicated that drug release

followed the zero order release pattern from creams. The release exponent value (n) for all formulation used to characterize the drug release mechanism and the obtained ' n ' values (0.6737 to 0.8919) for all formulations was more than 0.5, which indicated that the drug release followed Non-Fickian diffusion mechanism. This might be due to swelling property of the polymer used in cream.

Table No.6: Release Kinetic & Mechanism

Formulation code	Zero order (R ²)	First order (R ²)	Higuchi (R ²)	Korsmeyer- Peppas ₂	
				N	(R)
F1	0.987	0.957	0.915	0.672	0.971
F2	0.978	0.942	0.871	0.800	0.890
F3	0.989	0.957	0.890	0.821	0.877

F4	0.954	0.932	0.835	0.793	0.842
F5	0.975	0.991	0.955	0.840	0.910
F6	0.942	0.973	0.941	0.839	0.895
F7	0.975	0.978	0.926	0.868	0.892
F8	0.935	0.942	0.876	0.897	0.859
F9	0.946	0.953	0.897	0.836	0.893
F10	0.976	0.851	0.891	0.848	0.891

Figure No.7: First order release kinetics of F1 to F10

FigureNo.8: Higuchi kinetics of F1 to F10

Figure No.9: Korsmeyer-Peppas kinetics of F1 to F10

In vitro antifungal activity

The anti-fungal activity of optimized formulation was examined to determine the most potent formula against candida fungus. Figure 10 demonstrated that optimized formulation has the most potent anti-fungal activity supported by a 12 mm inhibition zone diameter. This could be justified by the antifungal action may be due to the presence of surfactant and penetration enhancer.

Fig No.10 In vitro antifungal activity.

a	Blank
b	Placebo
c	clotrimazole
d	Optimized formulation

Stability studies:-

Based on visual observation the optimized Clotrimazole cream (F10) for a period of 3 months. The optimized formulation (F10) was analyzed for clotrimazole content by UV spectrophotometer. The result showed that slight decrease in drug content was found when the Clotrimazole cream kept at $40\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 months. Since the overall degradation was not more than 3%.

Table No.7: Stability study of Clotrimazole cream:

Sr. No.	Time period for sampling	Drug content (%)
1.	Initial	96.5 ± 1.475
2.	After 1 month	96.2 ± 1.552

3.	After 2 month	95.7 ± 0.853
4.	After 3 month	95.6 ± 1.21

CONCLUSION

Topical route of application has a great potential as an effective and safe way to administer drug for its antifungal in effect. The concentration of emulsifying agent and permeation enhancer significantly affects the critical parameters of cream formulation cumulative amount release at 12 hours. *In vitro* permeation study showed that menthol enhanced the cumulative amount of drug from cream formulation. The topical cream formulation developed in this study showed the promising anti-fungal activity, further *in vivo* studies and can be extrapolated for further development in treatment of fungal disease.

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HOW TO CITE: Shankrayya M, Gurubasavaraj A M T, Chaithra R P, Pradeep U, Evaluating the Impact of Formulation Parameters on Permeation of Clotrimazole from Topical Creams, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 1, 1803-1814. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18298169>

